

An RPA-powered Simulated Phishing Campaign Solution for Assessing Human Susceptibility

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Abstract—The rise of social engineering attacks continues to pose a significant threat to individuals and organizations. In recent years, research has focused not only on developing effective cybersecurity defense strategies and mitigation approaches, but also on assessing an individual’s awareness of and susceptibility to such attack scenarios. Several approaches have been used, ranging from traditional methods, such as questionnaires designed to evaluate cybersecurity risky behavior and susceptibility to persuasion, which constitute a rather more static way to assess human susceptibility, to more contemporary practices, such as Simulated Social Engineering Campaigns, involving Phishing Campaigns and similar techniques. Simulated Phishing Campaigns offer the advantage of proactively identifying human-related susceptibility to phishing in a realistic manner, hence aiding in the prevention of real-world cyberattacks before they occur. However, more often than not, they require human intervention, which can be time- and cost-consuming as well as prone to error. This paper proposes the use of Robotic Process Automation (RPA) to automate Simulated Phishing Campaigns and, thus, enhance their efficiency and effectiveness. The proposed solution includes a user interface and back-end logic that automates the process of sending phishing emails and enumerates recipients’ interactions aiming at assessing phishing awareness. Furthermore, the proposed system is designed to be able to, eventually, also include the result of a persuasion susceptibility assessment with the aim to combine human vulnerability assessment approaches, co-present their results, and draw a more complete picture regarding an individual’s vulnerability. To assess the proposed system, a realistic use case scenario was employed to conduct an experiment in a lab environment demonstrating the potential offered by RPA technology in automating Simulated Phishing Campaigns and thus enhancing phishing awareness assessment strategies.

Index Terms—human susceptibility, phishing, robotic process automation, cybersecurity

I. INTRODUCTION

In the cybersecurity realm, many cyber-attacks are executed through social engineering practices [1]. The term “social engineering,” as utilized by cybersecurity experts, denotes the malicious manipulation of the human element inside an Infor-

mation and Communications Technology (ICT) environment. A prevalent social engineering tactic is the manipulation of human behavior in cyberspace using fraudulent emails, known as Phishing. [2]. Phishing occurs when a user is prompted to download a file or provide sensitive information (e.g., credentials) through a faked link, giving malicious individuals the opportunity to exploit this information or implant malware onto the victim’s machine. Phishing emails vary in terms of context, however, several patterns have been identified. Senders utilize known persuasion principles [3] to exploit human characteristics commonly referred to as human weaknesses in cyberspace [4], such as commitment based on the fact that humans tend to stay in line with commitments they have made in the past.

Educating individuals to identify and avoid known social engineering practices can be achieved through awareness-raising campaigns [5] or through simulated social engineering attacks, through the learn-through-experience methodology [6]. A simulated phishing campaign involves conducting many simulated phishing attacks during a specific and defined time frame. For such a campaign to be carried out successfully, several phishing email templates are developed for drafting emails that will be sent to the targets of the campaign. These templates are based on known persuasion principles and are filled out with content relevant to the recipient to achieve a more realistic experience. The way recipients interact with the emails is recorded and a report is generated, including the overall susceptibility status of the individuals involved in the campaign.

Nevertheless, the process of simulated phishing campaigns is a rather complicated operation. The extensive nature of a manually conducted campaign, combined with the fact that such campaigns are often executed by third-party organizations, leads to an increased cost. The system administrator or an authorized individual needs to contact the initiator of the campaign to agree on several campaign parameters, such

as the duration, intensity, and information handling of the entire operation. As a result, simulated phishing campaigns are usually one-time operations that aim to momentarily assess the phishing awareness of the personnel of an infrastructure.

In the process of investigating simulated phishing campaigns to automate such a procedure and mitigate its complexity and cost, this paper proposes the use of the RPA technology. According to the definition of IEEE [7], RPA is defined as “pre-configured software instance that uses business rules and pre-defined activity to complete the autonomous execution of a combination of processes, activities, transactions, and tasks in one or more unrelated software systems to deliver a result or service with human exception management”. A piece of software that performs this predefined tasks is often referred to as a software robot.

Based on the literature review that was performed, this paper proposes a low-cost and high-accuracy approach based on the RPA technology for automating simulated phishing campaigns, while it investigates benefits and drawbacks that emerge from such an implementation. The proposed proof-of-concept solution aims to allow the system administrator to setup key parameters through a user interface whereas the employment of RPA allows for further customization and offers the ability to launch such campaigns on a regular basis.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Chapter II reviews relevant initiatives that either aim to automate cybersecurity operations, by utilizing the RPA technology, or attempt to automate phishing operations in general; Chapter III provides a detailed description of the planning, design, and development of the proposed solution, while Chapter IV refers to the evaluation of the solution. Finally, Chapter V includes the closing remarks of this paper and the limitations of the proposed approach as well as the future steps that that could be followed towards its enhancement.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Robotic Process Automation

Automation in the cybersecurity sector is not a novel concept, while it has showcased significant promise in enhancing cybersecurity measures and reducing operational costs. For instance, Chen Zhong et al. in [8] established a system that considered the behavior of 29 expert cybersecurity analysts as they examined a set of alarms and firewall records. By automating the process and enabling the extraction of path patterns for attack mitigation, the suggested framework reduced operational costs and time investment requirements. On the other hand, Murugappan et.al. [9] explored the security risks associated with RPA and emphasized the importance of secure implementation and management. While RPA offers benefits such as cost savings, improved efficiency, and enhanced accuracy, inadequate security can lead to privacy issues, regulatory compliance violations, and potential penalties or business shutdowns. Their paper proposed a comprehensive security framework to address these risks and ensure secure deployment of RPA in organizations.

RPA technology has also been harnessed to aid in automating various cybersecurity processes. Adhikari et al. [10] used RPA in conjunction with other technologies to improve the security of complex aerospace systems. The findings demonstrated that, when compared to manually conducted Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) operations, RPA improved the process by enhancing the resilience of the systems. Addressing manual cybersecurity processes, an AI-based RPA system has been proposed by Kim et. al. [11] to automate threat log analysis. This system standardizes log formats, enhances threat prediction, and reduces human errors, offering a scalable solution for public and government organizations. Additionally, a novel UMLRPAsec [12] extension for RPA design introduces security-oriented formal modeling, allowing developers to address security concerns during the design stage and offering a structured approach to creating secure automated systems.

In the context of employee-focused cybersecurity initiatives, frameworks that integrate RPA tools with vulnerability assessment platforms like the ZAP scanner have been proposed [13]. These integrations, supported by languages such as ASL4RPA, enable automated cybersecurity testing for web applications, enhancing efficiency and vulnerability detection. Furthermore, RPA-driven solutions have been applied in signature verification within banking sectors, demonstrating the potential to eliminate human error and improve the accuracy of processes like account creation and document validation.

B. Simulated Phishing Campaigns

Phishing detection is among others, an important skill for individuals operating in a digital environment, in order to enhance cybersecurity and cyber hygiene. In the past few years, phishing awareness strategies are on the rise, such as gamified approaches and simulated phishing email campaigns. A gamified competition, the “Phish Derby,” [14] conducted at a large university, demonstrated the effectiveness of gamification in phishing detection. Employees competed by reporting phishing emails, and results highlighted that older employees outperformed younger ones, past performance predicted success, and personality traits like extraversion and agreeableness were correlated with poorer performance. These findings underscore the importance of motivating positive behaviors beyond traditional click-rate metrics.

When it comes to automating simulated phishing campaigns, efforts have led to the development of tools, such as the Social Engineering Toolkit (SET) [15], which was one of the earliest frameworks that were proposed to mitigate the financial and time expenses of manually conducted phishing campaigns. Dave Kennedy conceptualized and developed this open-source Python-based social engineering penetration testing application, which manages to simplify the process of sending phishing emails. However, SET does have certain limitations, among which are that it is a command line tool lacking a user-friendly interface while it covers highly specific operations which require adequate technical knowledge in

order to modify the existing code base of the framework and be further expanded.

With a focus on user-friendliness, KingPhisher [16] is a framework that was developed for simulating real-world phishing attacks in order to test and raise user awareness. This framework can be used to run campaigns either for basic awareness training or for more complex scenarios, where phishing emails aim for credential harvesting. However, the specific framework is no longer being maintained.

Another simulated Phishing Campaign automation initiative that it is worth mentioning is the Phishing Frenzy [17] framework, developed by Brandon McCann to assist penetration testers in handling phishing attacks more effectively, while still providing realistic phishing campaigns. Nonetheless, similar to the case of KingPhisher, the Phishing Frenzy framework has not been maintained for the past five (5) years.

The most popular solution, to the best of our knowledge, which has been utilized in several scientific studies [18], [19], [20], is the GoPhish framework, developed by Jordan Wright in late 2013. GoPhish is currently an open-source platform that automates simulated phishing attacks and creates a report detailing the results of each campaign. Furthermore, GoPhish's well-designed and implemented user interface makes it one of the most complete frameworks in terms of both automating a simulated phishing campaign and presenting each campaign's results. However, several limitations exist. For example, while it offers a user-friendly interface, advanced customization or integration with external tools requires significant technical knowledge and manual coding. Additionally, GoPhish may encounter scalability issues during large-scale campaigns, and its reporting features, although functional, lack the granularity and depth needed for detailed behavior analysis and compliance requirements. Moreover, GoPhish does not offer RPA capabilities, limiting its ability to simulate post-phishing user interactions such as credential harvesting or complex attack scenarios. Lastly, as an open-source solution, security updates and patches may be slower to roll out, potentially leaving it vulnerable to exploitation if not carefully maintained.

RPA's role in automating phishing simulations has evolved to encompass frameworks that analyze the interplay between persuasion principles, emotional triggers, and user profiles. These studies highlight the importance of understanding human vulnerabilities to design more effective phishing detection and prevention strategies. By incorporating emerging technologies like RPA, cybersecurity is becoming more robust, scalable, and adaptive to modern threats. However, despite the advancement of several phishing campaign frameworks that automate processes such as phishing email delivery, user interaction enumeration, and the presentation of campaign findings, a common limitation remains: none of these frameworks utilize RPA technology to fully automate phishing campaigns. As a result, further process customization or expansion beyond the predefined capabilities of these frameworks is not feasible and would require significant technical expertise to implement. This underscores the need for continued exploration of RPA's potential in enhancing phishing campaign automation and

contributing to strengthening the cybersecurity capacity of a digital environment.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The goal of the proposed proof-of-concept implementation was to successfully automate Simulated Phishing Campaigns through the employment of RPA technology while using a user-friendly workspace environment. The architectural design of the proposed solution was based on the following: i) the majority of operations should be conducted by the software robots' back-end operations. This is done to ensure a user-friendly experience, enabling users to efficiently set up and execute simulated phishing campaigns. Users should interact with the system and access its features without requiring expert knowledge; ii) To accomplish effective RPA automation of a Simulated Phishing Campaign, minimal to no human intervention should be required. The process of configuring a campaign should only require input from the Campaign's Initiator in order to determine the necessary parameters. This method aims to relieve the Campaign Initiator of the manual administration and execution of Simulated Phishing Campaigns; iii) The tasks of robots should be clearly defined as a series of distinct steps to be executed in a specific sequential order, enabling the automation of the process. By breaking down the process of a Simulated Phishing Campaign into smaller, distinct steps the proposed approach can imitate the actions that would otherwise be performed by a human. Furthermore, due to the robots' adherence to a standardized sequence of actions, the suggested approach ensures consistency and predictability, thereby enabling dependable and replicable outcomes.

Based on the objectives described above, the conceptual architecture of the proposed solution was designed and is presented in Figure 1 below, including the internal components, the external dependencies, and the entities that either initiate the Simulated Phishing Campaign operation or directly relate to the process. The interoperability between the sub-components is also showcased. In addition, the two basic personas participating in the proposed solution are included, namely the Campaign Initiator and the Targets of the campaign. The Campaign Initiator persona is the end-user that configures the parameters of the campaign and will ultimately receive the post-campaign report. On the other hand, the Target persona refers to the end-user group that will receive the phishing emails, which may be the personnel of an ICT ecosystem. The proposed solution comes as an adapter to an in-house developed RPA Framework, which - before the addition of the simulated phishing campaign functionality - was able to perform mouse actions, describe processes and schedule timed tasks. However, the implementation of the RPA Framework itself is out of the scope of this paper since it solely serves as the host of the proposed solution.

The Campaign Initiator is depicted as an external entity to the proposed framework, on the left side of the diagram. This is because, apart from the initial campaign configuration, the rest of the proposed solution's operations function without the need of human intervention. Thus, the sole role of the

Fig. 1. Conceptual Diagram

Campaign Initiator is to configure and initiate the Simulated Phishing Campaign process. However, if a Campaign Initiator decides to interfere, they can do so through the framework's User Interface.

Moreover, the "LDAP Directory", "SMTP Server" and "Database" components, located at the top of the diagram, are presented as external entities since all function regardless of the infrastructure that exists below and describe software services that interact with the RPA Framework. The "LDAP Directory" contains the user information storing directory and is accessed with the use of the LDAP protocol to retrieve the targets of the Simulated Phishing Campaign. The Database includes the MySQL database that is initialized with the templates of the phishing emails that are sent through the SMTP server.

The Targets group of the Simulated Phishing Campaign, similar to the Campaign Initiator, is also an external entity of the system. This entity includes the recipients of the phishing mails that are sent by the software robots; the interactions of these entities to the emails of the Simulated Phishing Campaign will be recorded to eventually produce the report of a campaign. In an ICT ecosystem, these targets may refer to the personnel whose phishing susceptibility will be assessed.

Moving to the central section of the diagram, the "RPA Framework" component represents the framework that hosts the proposed solution. By employing a "Plugin" architecture the proposed operations were added as a complementary component, rendering the proposed solution highly modular.

Inside the "RPA Framework" two different components are depicted, namely: the "Frontend", which represents the component responsible for the user interaction with the RPA framework, and the "Backend", which contains the logic and backend operations of the RPA framework. The Simulated Phishing Campaign Adapter module, as part of the RPA Framework's Backend, represents the solution proposed in this paper.

The Simulated Phishing Adapter contains a number of dedicated microservices, each one with specific responsibilities in order to mitigate system-wide failures. In more detail, the

Database Managing microservice handles database manipulation operations, such as the creation of new campaigns as well as the process of updating already existing ones. The Schedule Creating microservice generates the schedule of the Simulated Phishing Campaign and breaks down all the emails that need to be sent to target recipients into timed tasks that span across the specified duration of the campaign. The duration of the campaign is indicated by the starting and ending date provided set by the Campaign Initiator as part of the configuration of the campaign's parameters. Another parameter that is considered when generating the schedule is the total number of recipients that the campaign regards. Based on the notion that every phishing email template should be sent once to each of the campaign's recipients, each recipient adds a total of tasks to the schedule equal to the amount of the selected phishing emails that will be sent. Moreover, the generated schedule foresees leaving a two-day slack at the end of the campaign in order to capture any late-respondents.

Furthermore, the Task Executing microservice is responsible for executing the total of tasks included in the generated campaign schedule; the successful execution of a task results in a successfully sent phishing email. An important operation of the Task Executor is filling out the phishing emails with dynamic text and visual content to achieve a more realistic Simulated Phishing Campaign. In order to blend the phishing emails with legitimate ones, the emails of the campaign are pre-configured to be sent during working hours (i.e., 9a.m. to 5p.m.) since a higher email traffic is taking place during these hours. The interactions of the email recipients with the emails are monitored through the Interaction Enumerating microservice. Phishing emails contain images and hyperlinks that are not directly accessible, rather they are requested from the Interaction Enumerating microservice, which enumerates what was requested. For instance, an image request means that a recipient opened the mail, therefore, the image was loaded. On the other hand, a hyperlink request means that the recipient attempted to follow a link contained in the phishing email. Credential submission activities that take place on the landing pages to which several hyperlinks may lead are also being recorded. However, the actual values of the submitted credentials are not captured to preserve the security and privacy of the individuals involved in the Simulated Phishing Campaign.

Finally, the Report Creating microservice is responsible for producing a report, in a human-readable form, to describe the overall susceptibility posture of the individuals (i.e., targets) that were assessed. Valuable information for the creation of this report is the total number and type of interactions with the phishing emails performed during the campaign. These numbers are translated into insightful analytics and are depicted in corresponding charts to provide a more easily understandable overview of the overall phishing susceptibility of the targets.

A. Operational Flow

To design the flow of operation of the proposed solution, the "translation" of the tasks a human would take to complete the process of a Simulated Phishing Campaign was performed. The translation of the process in RPA tasks involves breaking down the Simulated Phishing Campaign into smaller, independent tasks that can be combined to form the entire process. These tasks were designed to be reusable in order to create additional RPA processes. As depicted in Figure 2, the first step a human operator would take would be to specify when the campaign will start and for how long it would last. After the duration of the campaign is defined, the human operator should know the mailing list of the targets of the campaign. The campaign is then initiated after a confirmation of the agreed parameters. When the end date of the campaign has been reached, the final step would be to present the results of the Simulated Phishing Campaign through a composed report.

Fig. 2. Flow diagram

The Simulated Phishing Campaign procedure starts at the front-end, where the Campaign Initiator configures key parameters, such as LDAP credentials, start and end dates, and a descriptive campaign name. Upon completion of the basic setup, the framework's robot attempts to retrieve users from the LDAP system. This process also confirms that the settings were configured accurately. Upon the completion of the retrieve process, the users are presented to the Campaign Initiator, signifying that access to the LDAP was achieved successfully. Upon completion of the Simulated Phishing Campaign setting, the Campaign Initiator may commence the execution of the campaign and await the assessment findings. The launch of the campaign execution triggers the personalization of phishing emails. Each user will get one instance of every phishing email type, created using phishing email templates, to eliminate bias and offer a clear perspective on the success rate of each email. After the phishing emails are created, they are scheduled for dispatch at designated times. The timeline is constructed based on the established start date and concludes two days prior to the planned finish date, accommodating the recording of late answers. Simultaneously, the Interaction Recorder monitors the targets' interactions with the received messages by enumerating the requested URLs and the submitted credentials, which is a continuous activity alongside the dispatching of emails until the campaign's completion date. Upon reaching the conclusion date, the campaign report is created. The report presents an

analysis of the assessment findings in both percentages and absolute figures, accompanied by bar chart visualizations, to assist the Campaign Initiator in comprehending the overall phishing vulnerability of the target group.

B. Phishing Email Templates

The conduction of a Simulated Phishing Campaign required the creation of phishing email templates to specify the overall form and appearance of the emails. The overall structure and layout of the emails was first defined, including the font, color scheme, and formatting to make emails look authentic and professional. The templates also contained variables in crucial parts of the email, such as the recipient's name, that would later be replaced with dynamically generated information, allowing for the customization and personalization of the phishing emails to make them more convincing and effective.

This process was repeated to create a total of 12 templates. These included emails that appeared to come from well-known authorities, such as a national bank, as well as emails that seemed like friendly messages from a co-worker. This process ensured that the templates were versatile and leveraged all the persuasion principles identified in relevant literature [3]. In brief, the persuasion principles and what they entail are as follows: i) Reciprocity: when an individual performs an act for someone, then people are more likely to do something for the said individual in return; ii) Scarcity: highlighting the limited availability of a product or service can increase its perceived value; iii) Authority: People follow the lead of credible, knowledgeable experts. Through demonstrating expertise or showcasing endorsements persuasiveness can be enhanced; iv) Consistency: people like to be consistent, so getting someone to agree to a small commitment makes them more likely to agree to a larger one later; v) Liking: people tend to say yes to those they know and like, therefore building rapport and finding common ground can increase likability and influence; vi) Consensus (Social Proof): presenting people with what others have chosen can convince them to make similar choices. An example of such phishing template is the following "Reforestation" e-mail, in Figure 3, utilising the commitment and consensus persuasion principles:

IV. APPLIED USE CASE

An experiment was carried out to evaluate the efficacy of the suggested method in this research by implementing a Simulated Phishing Campaign spanning one week, during which phishing emails were sent to a sample target population. The experiment's results were utilized to assess the proposed solution's capability to dispatch phishing emails to designated targets, enumerate interactions executed by the recipients, maintain accuracy throughout the campaign's duration, and ultimately produce a post-campaign report, thereby automating the process of Simulated Phishing Campaigns via RPA. Before the campaign commenced, all participants completed a questionnaire assessing their susceptibility to persuasion principles, the results of which were incorporated into the post-campaign report to derive insights from the comparison of static and

All forested areas of the country that are burning should remain forested and be reforested

Once again, suddenly as soon as there is interest in investments, everything around us burns. So many fire outbreaks on the same day is no coincidence. It is necessary for all Greek politicians to prove to us that they have not hidden agenda. We demand that all forested areas of the country that are burning remain forested and that politicians of all parties commit to reforestation. We need your help ! Sign by pressing the button below and make our voice heard.

Fig. 3. Reforestation template

dynamic evaluations. However, the analysis of this comparison is outside the scope of this work and will be addressed in further research.

A. Deployment

The proposed system has two external dependencies, namely, an LDAP Server containing the details of the personnel and an SQL database that stores system-related information such as names and dates of the campaigns. The LDAP Server was instantiated and filled with information from 10 individuals. This information regarded their email address as well as their first and last name. Similarly, an instance of an SQL database was deployed infrastructure-internally. However, no initial configuration was necessary as the tables and data are generated dynamically during the runtime of the proposed system.

B. Initiation of the Simulated Phishing Campaign

As displayed in Figure 4, the operation of Simulated Phishing Campaign is composed of 6 distinct steps. After the “Start” task, which defines the start of an RPA Framework process, the necessary steps for the automation of the Simulated Phishing Campaign are “Campaign Start”, “LDAP Set Up”, “Send Mail” and “Generate Report”. The steps “Connect to HV” and “Arsenal and Targets” were added to complement the proposed system and for confirmation purposes, respectively.

Fig. 4. Simulated Phishing Campaign RPA process

Once the necessary as well as complementary tasks are placed in the correct order, the next step is the configuration of the steps, where this is required. Tasks that require configuration contain a circled “x” in their body indicating that further actions are required. The first step in the order that requires input is the “Campaign Start” task. The successful configuration of all tasks of the RPA Process displays the available Targets in the Arsenal and Targets task.

C. Evaluating the proper function of the Simulated Phishing Campaign solution

In the experiment conducted to assess the feasibility of the solution, the LDAP directory was instantiated with the details of ten (10) individuals, who became the targets of the campaign. While the campaign was active, a total of one hundred and forty (140) phishing mails were sent as well as received, out of which one hundred and one (101) were opened. A total of seventy six (76) clicks on the contained URLs was recorded, out of which forty six (46) times the targeted individuals submitted their credentials. Finally, a total of seven (7) file requests were recorded. The participants of the experiment confirmed that the numbers were accurate. A post-campaign report was generated with the collected results, which is showcased in Figure 5 below. The findings of the Simulated Phishing Campaign were accurately presented in the report including both the amount and the types of interactions with the phishing emails. The results of the experiment showed that the automated Simulated Phishing Campaign was effective in sending the created phishing emails, attracting interactions, as well as enumerating and presenting them in an intuitive report.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper explored further applications of the RPA technology in the realm of cybersecurity and proposed the automation of Simulated Phishing Campaigns. By describing the process of a Simulated Phishing Campaign in distinct subsequent steps and developing the corresponding User Interface as well

Automatically Generated Report for "PilotCampaign" Campaign:

Report Overview:

Total e-mails sent:	140
Total emails opened:	101
Total malicious links clicked:	78
Total credentials submitted:	46
Total file downloads:	7

Statistic Analysis:

- 72% of the phishing mails sent were opened.
- 54% of the malicious links were clicked
- 32% of the mails harvested credentials successfully.
- 8% of the malicious files were downloaded.

Campaign Description:

Campaign Named : PilotCampaign started at 17/3/2022 and the last email was sent at 23/3/2022 signaling the end of the campaign.

Throughout the campaign 10 individuals were tested with a total of 140 mails. All participants received exactly the same mails in order the test to be as objective as possible.

Findings:

While the campaign was active, a total of 101 phishing mails were opened out of the 140 that were originally sent. Inside those emails, two kinds of links could be included. One that led on a "malicious" webpage and one that requested an equally could-be-malicious file. We enumerated a total of 78 clicks on the malicious webpage URLs, of which 46 individuals went on to submit their credentials on the particular webpage. The malicious file requests were counted at a total of 7.

"malicious" webpage and one that requested an equally could-be-malicious file. We enumerated a total of 78 clicks on the malicious webpage URLs, of which 46 individuals went on to submit their credentials on the particular webpage. The malicious file requests were counted at a total of 7.

Interaction Figures:

Fig. 5. Post-campaign report

as the necessary backend functionality, a prototype, proof-of-concept system was presented. The proposed system is capable of attracting and enumerating the amount and types of interactions conducted by the personnel of an ICT infrastructure, who are the targets of the campaign. The results of the campaign were presented together with an initial human susceptibility assessment, providing a more complete view of the vulnerability of the targets of the campaign.

Overall, the results of the experiment support the feasibility and potential effectiveness of automating through RPA the process of Simulated Phishing Campaigns. However, further research is needed to confirm these findings and to explore the potential limitations and risks of automating simulated social engineering attacks through RPA for cybersecurity awareness assessment. The proposed solution does not come without some limitations, which should be considered when interpreting the results. Specifically, the proposed system is a proof-of-concept solution for automating Simulated Phishing Campaigns and further research may be required to ensure its effectiveness of assessing underlying phishing susceptibility.

Next steps towards the enhancement of the proposed system include further expansion to discover and evaluate additional automation of cybersecurity operations through RPA such as Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) operations concerning the Targets of the campaign as well as, automation of the initial persuasion susceptibility assessment to result in a more comprehensive solution. Finally, a real-world use case of the proposed solution could be applied in an attempt to conduct an accurate phishing susceptibility assessment operation.

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